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АНАЛИЗ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕСТУПЛЕНИЙ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ

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ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC CRIMES IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Аннотация

Данная статья посвящена проблеме развития экономических преступлений в Казахстане. При этом уделяется внимание анализу показателей как, мошенничество, киберпреступления, а также коррупция. Кроме этого приводится система мер по сокращению коррупции и экономических преступлений в целом.

Abstract

This article is devoted to the problem of the development of economic crimes in Kazakhstan. At the same time, attention is paid to the analysis of indicators such as fraud, cybercrime, as well as corruption. In addition, a system of measures to reduce corruption and economic crimes in general is provided.

Ключевые слова: экономические преступления, мошенничество, киберпреступления, коррупция.

Keywords: economic crimes, fraud, cybercrime, corruption.

With the transition to a market system, the country's economy has undergone significant changes. Privatization mechanisms and private property appeared. In the process of life, the state practically did not attach particular importance to crimes related to encroachment on commodity-money and property relations. These types of offenses were classified as crimes, only in case of significant damage, but were not classified into a separate group. From which it follows that the concept of economic crime was formed relatively recently.

Complexity, versatility, and a stably continuing trend towards change make it difficult to accurately interpret such a definition as "economic crime". The term "economic crime" means: Economic crime covers a wide range of offenses, from financial crimes committed by banks, tax evasion, illicit capital heavens, money laundering, crimes committed by public officials (like bribery, embezzlement, traffic of influences, etc.) among many others [1].

Economic crime, also known as financial crime, refers to illegal acts committed by an individual or a group of individuals to obtain a financial or professional advantage. The principal motive in such crimes is economic gain [2].

Economic crime is defined as any "illegal act committed by an individual or a group of individuals to obtain a financial or professional advantage". Typical forms of economic crime as including capital investment frauds, misleading consumers, fraudulent bankruptcy, tax evasion, credit and insurance fraud, credit card fraud, cybercrime, corruption and money laundering [3].

It is important to form a unified scientific approach to the study of economic crimes, based on an assessment of the current level of economic crimes. In 1-st figure shows the dynamics of economic crimes for the period 2016–2020.

Figure 1 Dynamics of economic crimes for the period 2016-2020 years.

Figure 1 shows that in 2020 it can be seen that the dynamics of economic crimes increased by 241 crimes or by 22.8% compared to 2019. At the same time, the greatest economic crimes are related to issuing invoices

without actually performing work, shipping goods, which amounted to 438 crimes or 33.8% of all. (Table 1)

Table 1

Analysis of economic offenses in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2019-2020

	2019 year	2020 year	Change 2020 to 2019,%
Number of economic crimes	1053	1294	22,8
Of them			
Creation and management of the financial pyramid	24	180	
Issuance of invoices without actual performance of work, shipment of goods	285	438	153,7
Production, storage, sale of counterfeit securities	254	213	83,4
Evasion of taxes and other obligatory payments to the budget	92	97	105,4
Evasion of customs payments and fees	53	30	56,6
Violation of rules and marking order	75	65	86,7
Legalization of money or property obtained by criminal means	42	39	92,9
Illegal receipt of a credit or misuse of a budget credit	26	21	80,8
Economic Contraband	39	58	148,7
Non-return from abroad of funds in nat. or foreign currency	40	23	57,5
Other crimes	123	130	105,7

It can also be emphasized that in 2020, crimes related to the actions of financial pyramids increased. So, if in 2019 there were 24 such offenses, then in 2020 the number of such offenses increased by 156 crimes, which amounted to 180. In this regard, individuals as a result of the actions of economic criminals suffered financial losses in the amount of up to 6.4 billion tenge.

Due to the growth of economic crimes, according to the Prosecutor General's Office, there was a twofold increase in the amount of damage from these offenses. So, if in 2019 the damage amounted to 62.9 billion tenge, then in 2020 - 164.8 billion tenge. The increase amounted to 101.9 billion tenge. At the same time, 94.1% of this amount is the damage caused to the state (155.1 billion tenge).

Some types of economic crime, such as bribery and corruption or fraudulent activities, it's harder to predict and track, they can result in severe fines and associated consequences such as loss of business or damage to brand and reputation.

The leaders in terms of losses were: violation of antitrust laws, misuse of insider information, tax fraud, money laundering, bribery and corruption. Some of these types of economic crimes also incur remedial costs and fines.

Fraud is typically transactional in nature and can be effectively tracked and prevented, reducing the negative financial impact on for organization. Over the past 3 years, over 95 thousand crimes have been registered in the country, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Dynamics of registered fraudulent crimes in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2018-2020

Note - Compiled by the author from the source [4]

Figure 2 shows that there is an increase in registered fraudulent crimes in Kazakhstan. So, in 2018, the number of these crimes was 29282 units, then in 2020 there was an increase of 4477 units or 15.3%, which amounted to 33759 crimes. The share of these crimes remains quite high at 17-20% and ranks second after thefts. Against the background of the growth of the practice of online shopping and online services, there is an increase in the number of Internet fraud by 2 times. (from 7769 in 2018 to 14220 in 2020). The peculiarity of such actions is that in the process of committing criminal offenses, criminals use online ad platforms (OLX, Kolesa.kz, Krisha.kz), banking application (Kaspi.kz) and microfinance organizations. With the use of these online platforms, fictitious ads are created, the price of the offered goods is significantly reduced, thereby attracting future victims in the face of gullible buyers. As the development of information technologies takes place, there are also changes in the actions of intruders, whose activities are associated with the processes of digitalization.

Cybercrimes in the modern world are becoming one of the most dangerous and difficult to detect. According to the data of the Committee on Legal Statistics

and Special Accounts of the Republic of Kazakhstan, in 2021 the number of criminal offenses in the field of informatization and communications increased by 6% compared to 2020. At the same time, the largest share falls on unauthorized access to information, to an information system or an information and communication network (Article 205) and accounts for 70% of all cybercrimes [5].

Taking into account the expansion and strengthening of digitalization processes, the number and severity of cybercrimes will increase in the future. This will create new and transform existing threats to the economic security of SMEs. In this regard, the task of management becomes the creation and development of specialized departments at enterprises to counter information security threats emanating both from their own personnel and from the external environment. This requires significant expenses. Thus, according to the research company Astute Analytica, the costs of information security in the world in the coming years will increase by an average of 13.4% annually. It is expected that by 2027, its global spending will reach \$345 billion, compared to \$162 billion in 2021 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Expected costs of information security in the world 2021-2027

Note - Compiled by the author from the source [6]

It is obvious that small enterprises that do not have sufficient resources will not be able to effectively counteract cyber threats on their own. There is a "blurring of boundaries" of certain types of threats. All of them are becoming more or less digital, which is a consequence of the penetration of digital technologies into all business processes and management processes of enterprises.

Digitalization makes it possible to increase the information openness of the enterprise, hence its vulnerability to malicious influence. SMEs by their nature are becoming digital in many ways. This is due to the widespread use of digital platforms [7]. In a number of industries, this leads to a radical change in business models.

Thus, in the context of the rapidly growing digitalization of the socio-economic system, significant changes are taking place in the organization of ensuring the economic security of enterprises.

Corruption in modern Kazakhstan is systemic and widespread in all regions of the country and at all levels of state and municipal government. The greatest danger is the corruption of officials.

Since the first days of state independence, Kazakhstan has been purposefully and gradually following the course of creating effective institutions and mechanisms for combating corruption that meet international standards.

The main strategic document of our country, Decree of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 986 dated December 26, 2014 "On the Anti-Corruption Strategy of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2015-2025", reflecting Kazakhstan's principled position on this important issue, serves as the basis of the state's anti-corruption policy in the coming years. Assessing the results of the implementation of the Anti-Corruption Strategy in Kazakhstan, it is necessary to turn to the assessment from the outside world.

The indicator of the level of corruption in the world "Corruption Perception Index" (CPI), compiled by the international rating organization Transparency International (TI), is one of the most authoritative evaluation systems in the field of studying the prevalence of corruption.

Since the beginning of the implementation of the Anti-Corruption Strategy, Kazakhstan's indicators in the CPI have a steady tendency to improve (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Dynamics of changes in the CPI of Kazakhstan for 2016-2026.

Note - Compiled by the author from the source [8]

This, of course, reflects a positive assessment of the ongoing policy in the country and the comprehensive anti-corruption measures taken.

Kazakhstan scored 38 points in the ranking of countries on the Corruption Perception Index in 2020 and took 94th place, improving its performance over the past 5 years. The results of 2020 are the best for Kazakhstan for the entire time it has been in the Transparency International rating.

The growth of Kazakhstan's positions in the Corruption Perception Index rating against the background of the emergency in the health sector and threats to the

stability of democratic institutions indicates the progressive work of the country in combating corruption.

To date, Kazakhstan is included in the ratings of other reputable international organizations, reflecting the level of corruption. The results of the studies of 9 rating agencies that were used in calculating the CPI are shown in Table 2.

According to Transparency International Kazakhstan experts, Kazakhstan's retention of its positions in the CPI rating against the background of the global crisis of democracy and the growth of transnational and local corruption indicates the positive dynamics of the country in combating corruption.

Table 2

Kazakhstan's positions on rating agencies for 2019-2020

Rating Agencies	Indicator	2019	2020
Bertelsmann Foundation Transformation Index	corruption policy	33	33
Economist Intelligence Unit Country Ratings	level of corruption	20	20
Freedom House Nations In Transit Ratings	level of corruption	24	24
Global Insight Country Risk Ratings	corruption risk	35	47
IMD World Competitiveness Yearbook	bribery and corruption	55	61
PRS International Country Risk Guide	corruption	43	58
Varities Of Democracy Project	political corruption	17	17
World Economic Forum	perception of corruption	47	47
World Justice Project Rule Of Law Index	absence of corruption	36	38

Note - Compiled by the author from the source [9]

The annual rating of global competitiveness of the Institute of Management Development (The IMD World Competitiveness Ranking) is also of interest. In this study, 342 indicators, which are divided into four groups, assess countries: the state of the economy (includes macroeconomic indicators), government efficiency (including the level of corruption), the state of the business environment and infrastructure development. According to the results of the 2020 study, the Republic of Kazakhstan ranked 42nd (Table 3).

In 2019, Kazakhstan ranked 34th, so in 2020 it dropped by 8 positions compared to last year. The list of leading countries includes Singapore, Denmark,

Switzerland, the Netherlands, Hong Kong, Sweden, Norway, Canada, the UAE, the USA and Taiwan. In total, 63 countries are represented in the world ranking of competitiveness of economies. The deterioration of the position in the global competitiveness ranking is due to the outbreak of the coronavirus epidemic, which affected the level of development of the country's economy and the well-being of the population. To further improve the effectiveness of the government, experts from the Institute for Management Development recommend improving the state of the institutional and social sphere, business legislation and paying special attention to national security and anti-corruption issues.

Kazakhstan's position in the IMD World Competitiveness Ranking for 2019-2020.

Indicator	2019	2020
World Competitiveness Rating	34	42
1. Economic activity	45	48
Domestic economy	48	41
International trade	56	60
External investments	39	48
Busyness	23	33
Prices	35	16
2. Government efficiency	21	29
Public finances	22	23
Tax policy	15	16
Institutional environment	42	50
Legislation in business	25	28
Social order	29	38
3. Business efficiency	29	34
Productivity and efficiency	36	40
Labor market	11	32
Finance	41	47
Management practice	19	19
Relationships and values	24	29
4. Infrastructure	43	51
Basic infrastructure	25	31
Technological infrastructure	51	52
Scientific infrastructure	53	58
Health and environment	57	57
Education	26	44
Note - Compiled by the author from the source [10]		

Combating corruption has become a priority for consideration by international organizations, as well as at the global level by politicians and scientists. It is necessary to create conditions such as public control, transparency of government, etc. Another, no less

important condition is the development of effective administrative and legal means, tougher measures of responsibility. All this is impossible without an effective anti-corruption policy of the state. The system of measures to reduce corruption is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 System of measures to reduce the scale of corruption activities

Depending on the technologies used in the course of combating corruption, methods of influencing the ethical basis of the behavior of civil servants can be divided into traditional (adoption of regulatory and advisory documents, conducting training events) and electronic (publication of income declarations using electronic platforms, procurement for public needs in electronic form, etc.).

The greatest effectiveness of the impact of ethical and moral norms on compliance with anti-corruption prohibitions, restrictions and requirements can be achieved by ensuring the widespread use of these methods in their entirety.

It seems that the state and municipal service should create organizational conditions for compliance with ethical requirements: unity of ethical requirements, stability of the state and municipal service, social and legal protection of the civil servant, balance of legal restrictions and social guarantees provided to the civil servant.

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